
E- Commerce in Banking Sector

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Abstract:

Electronically-based payment systems have been in operation since the 1960s and have been expanding rapidly as well as growing in complexity. However, in most of the major industrialized countries, an inverse relationship exists between the volume and the number of transactions handled electronically. The Internet is experiencing rapid growth which is being largely driven by new commercial users of the network. Other commercial on-line services provided by companies such as CompuServe, America On-line and Prodigy is also expanding rapidly.

Introduction:

With the rapid expansion of the Internet, there are a number of initiatives underway for the creation of a secure cost-effective payment system which will be able to support growing commercial activities on the network. Although electronic payment systems for large payments have been in operation for some time, rapidly expanding volumes of foreign exchange and securities trading are increasingly at variance with the requirements for a cost-effective and efficient electronic payment system for making low value payments. Current progress in establishing such payment systems on the Internet is examined.

E-Commerce: It is a way of doing business transactions via the internet. E-commerce or e-business is based on the electronic processing and transmission of data, including text, sound, and video. E-commerce as it is commonly known is the use of technology to conduct financial transactions online. Commerce on the Internet is already a reality. The communication facilities which are on offer are rapidly become integrated as core business tools (Cronin, 1994). The emphasis to date has been on use of the Internet for

communications with customers and other companies operating on collaborative ventures. However, an increasing number are concentrating on transactions between businesses and on-line sales.

E-Banking: It allows customers of a financial institution to conduct financial transactions on a secure website operated by the institution, which can be a retail or virtualbank, credit union or building society. To access a financial institution's online banking facility, a customer having personal Internet access must register with the institution for the service, and set up some password (under various names) for customer verification. The password for online banking is normally not the same as for telephone banking. Financial institutions now routinely allocate customer numbers (also under various names), whether or not customers intend to access their online banking facility.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To study of payment systems through E-Banking and their role in respect to global trade and investment.
2. To review the various existing payments systems and concludes that a cost

effective and efficient electronic means for small value payments has yet to be established on a universal global basis.

3. To understand current developments in the expansion of the Internet as well as other broadly uses in E- commerce & Banking sector.

Methodology of the Study:

This paper is prepared on the basis of secondary sources of data, such as books, study material of professional courses, government, websites and some extent primary observations of the researchers.

Payment Systems through E-Banking:

Money and monetary systems have also been strongly linked to the role of the state. In the medieval period, money largely meant gold or silver coins whose weight and fitness were guaranteed by the ruler under whose authority they were issued. For a long period of history, official mints were established which would convert bullion into an equivalent weight of coins, minus a fee. In the 20th century, issuance of currency has been jealously guarded by the nation state and economic policy increasingly has been exercised indirectly through the monetary system using interest rates.

1. National systems of exchange: The development of money has been inextricably associated with the growth of trade and commerce. Monetary exchange and banking systems then developed rapidly as foreign and domestic trade expanded exponentially following the onset of the industrial revolution. Although commodity-based money dates back to antiquity, money in its present primarily token form (i.e., money that does not exist in any physical form but takes the form of financial claims on banks and other financial institutions) has only assumed predominance during the past 100 years. However, over the past 40 years, growth in international trade, which has exceeded the expansion of GDP at the

national level, has resulted in a global economy which increasingly has no place for economic and monetary policies which are pursued purely at the national level.

2. International systems of exchange:

International trade has grown significantly due to LPG policy and with it the associated monetary flows. More recently, the globalization have led to a spectacular growth in the value of non-trade-related financial transactions. Every transaction whether trade- or non-trade-related gives rise to obligations that need to be settled through a transfer of money between the parties involved. Settlement of non-trade-related and large value trade transactions is increasingly based on the electronic large value payment systems which have been developed since the 1960s. Together this has led to a major expansion in payment and settlement systems. These now handle payment volumes on a daily basis which collectively dwarf economic output in the main industrial countries.

3. Banking and Securities markets: Non-trade related international and domestic financial transactions have grown substantially both in absolute terms and relative to the growth in trade. Elaborate settlement systems are being developed to contain the burgeoning risks which are involved. The overall rate of increase has been substantial in the past 15 years. The past 25 years has seen a progressive globalization of world securities markets. While the speculative flow of funds into the world's emerging equity markets has declined from their peak in 1994, commentators identify them as a key source of future growth in the late 1990s. Standard Chartered Bank estimates that the size of emerging markets in terms of market capitalization is set to double to 4 trillion US dollars within the next five years, whereas others estimate that if present growth rates continue, these new markets could account for around half the world's equity market

capitalization by 2015 (*Financial Times*, 1994b). When messages are on free format (unrecognized universally) recipients have to interpret and to rekey them, involving higher levels of cost, more time and making the systems much more prone to the introduction of errors. At the same time there is a countervailing pressure to settle transactions, particularly those relating to securities, more quickly.

4. Payment & Settlement Systems: A mixture of different payment systems has evolved to service the growing requirements of both trade- and non-trade-related commerce. In the majority of cases, these systems operate as closed proprietary networks, creating incompatibilities between different systems. There is a particularly sharp division between the payment and settlements systems which are used for large value transfers and those which are available to settle smaller payments, particularly on a cross-border basis. This has led to an inverse relationship between the volume and the number of transactions. It has also further accentuated the division between large multi-national corporations and smaller enterprises wishing to utilize electronic systems for making payments. These large corporations seek to minimize the costs of transfers within their operations while preserving the legal integrity and tax status of the companies concerned. Smaller companies which do not have access to these networks are forced to rely on a paper-based system of documentary credits. These are generally very time-consuming as well as costly to buyer and seller alike.

5. National Payment Systems: Electronic payment systems are not new and have been around in some form for several decades. The volumes passing through wholesale systems are huge and it is useful to provide some indications of the scale of monetary flows which are involved. According to the Bank for International Settlements (BIS), it takes less than three business days for

Japan's interbank funds transfer systems to generate turnover equivalent to the country's annual economic output and around four days in Germany. However, both the volume and scale of these financial flows are increasingly removed from the day-to-day reality of making payments within and across borders for goods and services. International large value payments are increasingly intertwined. In Switzerland the proportion of large value payments which are one end of a foreign exchange transaction is already 90%. Expectations are that as finance becomes even more global in scope, then similar proportions will exist in some of the other major financial centers. This creates a push for real time settlement, ultimately on a global scale linking all the national large payment systems together (*Economist*, 1993).

6. Correspondent Banking: In contrast to the inter-bank settlement systems which have been developed for large value payments; other cross-border transactions are based on older payment architecture. The correspondent banking system remains widely in use throughout the world. It is also used where banking systems are fragmented, for example the United States, where it is used to facilitate payments between local regional banks by using large money center or payment banks. The correspondent banking system, although now ingrained after centuries of established practice, has become increasingly outdated. Its principal disadvantage lies in the requirement to involve three and sometimes even more parties to carry out the transfer of a single payment.

7. Payment Messaging Systems:

The demands for international settlement of currency and securities transactions have increased, electronic payment systems for large payments have developed. SWIFT, which stands for the Society for Worldwide Interbank Financial Telecommunication, currently dominates the field of interbank

messaging but is increasingly facing competition from other networks. Although the SWIFT system enjoys world-wide acceptance it is dependent on the same heritage of correspondent banks which form the basis for all low value cross-border transfers. SWIFT has more recently has been examining other opportunities to provide 'value-added' services including messaging associated with the global securities markets. It is generally accepted that a point will soon be reached where more traditional means of settlement using telex and facsimile will no longer be able to cope (*Financial Times*, 1994h). SWIFT is therefore focusing its attention on the requirements for global settlement of large value payments. Its existing proprietary network and charging structure is simply not cost effective when making lower value payments. In recent years, other competing cross-border electronic payment systems have been established.

7. Checks and Bank Transfers: Despite the development of electronic payment systems, business-to-business payments are still predominantly made using non-electronic funds transfer (checks or telegraphic transfer). In the US, despite the development of an array of automated systems, most businesses continue to bill their customers with paper invoices and to make payments to suppliers using paper checks. The same inverse relationship between payment volume (in terms of transaction volume) and aggregate payment value is mirrored in all the other industrialized countries where the percentage of business-to-business payments made electronically is frequently even lower than the 12.5% in the US. Paper-based payment systems are an increasingly costly anachronism in an age which permits cost effective global electronic communications systems. Individual businesses have also been reluctant to move to electronic methods, preferring instead to focus on automating internal administrative processes

and in some cases capitalizing on the float benefits which accrue as a result of payments in transit.

8. Credit Card Payment Systems: Credit and debit cards are rapidly growing in significance as the preferred method of settling small value payments associated with the purchase of specific goods and services. Separate electronic clearing and settlement systems have been established by the major credit card companies. Both MasterCard and Visa have established their own networks which are used for verifying transactions world-wide. Electronic point of sale terminals permit card details to be verified in less than 15 seconds with networks linking the merchant, the credit card processor and the card issuer world-wide. These networks are growing rapidly as the trend for consumers to make payments by credit card in place of writing a cheque continues to grow. The growth in credit card usage confirms the basic demand which exists for more efficient electronically based payment systems.

9. Cash and Automatic Teller Machines (ATMs): Despite the development of electronic payment systems, modern industrial economies still function to a large extent on cash payments. In the United Kingdom, around 85% of payments by volume are still made in this way (Association for Payment Clearing Services, 1994). Although cash payments represent the direct converse of electronic forms of payment, cash delivery is itself increasingly based on the huge base of Automatic Teller Machines (ATMs) which are being increasingly networked together to permit customers to collect cash from different banks as well as in other countries. ATM and credit card networks are linked in that VISA and MasterCard holders have long enjoyed the facility to draw cash from ATMs. A number of companies, including NatWest in the UK, are developing smart card technologies, which may ultimately

bridge the gap between ATM networks for delivering cash and the requirement to make electronic payments. NatWest are leading a consortium to develop smart card technology to develop an 'electronic purse' which with suitable equipment could also be used to transact payments on the Internet.

Development of Internet Payments System:

1. Development of Payment systems:

Markets of any sort involve transactions, right through to the point when the seller has been paid by the buyer. Until that point, the whole transaction remains uncertain. The more primitive the system, then the longer the delay is between undertaking to pay and actual payment, and the greater is the uncertainty. The Internet offers the prospect of a highly cost effective payment system for low value transactions. The technologies involved are able offer nearly to instantaneous settlement of transactions.

At present Internet customers have a limited set of options for making payments? The simplest option is to provide details of a credit card number and transmit this information to the merchant vendor usually using an alternative to electronic mail, either the telephone or fax. A number of enterprises currently trading on the Internet have opted for this payment method.

2. Digitized 'e-cash' Systems: A number of companies are developing payment systems which permit direct payments to be made anonymously. Payment takes the form of encoded messages representing the encrypted equivalent of digitized money. The aim is to be able to effect payment directly without requiring the use of intermediaries. A number of trials are presently under way to test the concepts which are involved. One of the leading firms which is developing an 'e-cash' system is Digi Cash, which has previously been involved in developing smart card technologies. Payments consist of uniquely

coded digital tokens which are established in such a way as to prevent duplication or fraud. Under the DigiCash scheme, customers would use local currency to buy an equivalent amount of digital cash from a bank. One of its key attractions is that it avoid the time and expense associated with becoming an approved credit card accepting merchant. Anyone will be able to set up a business and receive e-cash once the system is operating fully.

3. Payment Clearing Systems: A number of companies are attempting to overcome the security issues involved in handling payments on the Internet by establishing electronic clearing systems. Essentially the service on offer involves a system of secure messages which permit buyer and seller to communicate with each other, while also permitting instructions to make payment to be sent via the message/payment clearer, frequently using existing proprietary networks. First Virtual checks with the buyer that a particular transaction is to go ahead before arranging the appropriate account debit. First Virtue's initial aim is to permit businesses to receive income for services (such as publications) over the Internet where traditional payment methods would be uneconomic. In addition to facilitating debit or credit card payments, CyberCash will also provide independent electronic payment services. Accounts are established directly with CyberCash and maintained on the basis of an account holder's CyberCash key and not on direct user identity.

4. Credit Card-Based Systems: The major credit companies have been the only established financial institutions actively investing in future payment systems on the Internet. Credit card based payment systems have some limitations already identified earlier in the paper. Nevertheless, telephone-based credit card payments currently account for the majority of Internet commercial transactions. A secure and

efficient method to transmit credit card details will clearly be welcomed as a major step forward. A number of initiatives are underway. Both of the major credit card companies have linked up with software houses to develop the encryption software systems which will be required. Visa and Microsoft announced that they were jointly developing software based on a security architecture which will enable customers to make purchases using coded credit card, debit card and charge card numbers on-line.

5. Smart Card Based Systems:

Some observers believe that the only way in which payments over the Internet can be made secure is to physically separate authentication from the process which provides the communication links between buyer and seller. A number of companies are therefore examining the use of smart card readers linked to a personal computer. A smart card used to store money in the same way as a phone card would make it possible to separate authentication from the payment process. Smart cards technology would permit them to be charged up with cash at an ATM or separately using a proprietary bank network. The value in the smart card could then be transferred securely and anonymously over the Internet.

Limitations:

1. It requires the buyer to incur the additional expense and inconvenience of conveying credit card details and requires that the seller is accredited by a merchant acquirer/credit card processor.
2. It is also relatively costly since credit card merchant acquirers generally charge premiums for handling telephone-based sales. There is a general unwillingness to make personal credit card details available in this form, since both buyer and seller are exposed to fraud.
3. Difficulties which have been identified with the present system include the fact that banks run up large and unmonitored overdrafts during the day, exposing

members of the system to the risk that one might fail before payments had been completed with a dependence on 'unwinding' payments as the remedy for failure.

4. There is increasing pressure to use messaging as a result of falling settlement times. These have meant that it is increasingly difficult to trade confirmations in paper form.
5. The fundamental difficulty with establishing electronic payment systems on the Internet is that system was specifically designed to facilitate the free exchange of information.
6. Credit card payment systems have proved to be highly vulnerable to fraud. Credit cards can be stolen from their owners and then misused, and merchants accepting credit card payments can fraudulently fail to deliver goods.

Conclusion:

There are signs of increasing divergence between the existing electronic large value payment systems and the requirement for a globally-based electronic payment system which can process low value payments cost effectively. The former systems are based on proprietary closed systems architectures whose underlying technology is often mainframe-based and where communications are restricted to leased circuits. In addition, large value payment systems are increasingly becoming devoted to the processing of large foreign exchange and securities transactions which are largely divorced from the real trade in goods and services. This aggravates the inverse relationship which already exists between large volumes of transactions which are being processed in paper form compared to a much smaller number of very large payments which are processed electronically. New trading opportunities are being established as a result of the growth of the Internet and other on-line networks.

Many bankers remain skeptical that Internet-based payment can and will emerge. They believe that they will prove to be largely peripheral to established unchanged patterns of retailing and commerce along with their associated payment systems. However, the evidence is pointing to an alternative consensus. The result is likely to be the creation of a new global commercial market place which permits goods to be ordered and paid for electronically irrespective of location.

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